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Some complex particular solutions of a first integral of Navier-Stokes equations

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The factor that a first integral of the Navier-Stokes equations was constructed, opens a new horizon in the search for complex type solutions of this physical mathematical problem. The governing equations in terms of complex variables allows the pursuit for purely complex viscosity solutions. In this paper a complex first integral of the Navier-Stokes equations for steady flow was solved. The three purely complex particular solutions were attained without boundary condition, therefore for the complex plane as a whole.

1. Introduction

The occurrences of first integral of Navier-Stokes equations help to envision new possibilities for understanding and treatment of these elusive equation (Scholle et al. 2011, Clebsch. 1859). An expected curiosity that arises as result of this work is that from the difficulty and lack of solutions on the real plane, comes an abundance of solutions on the complex plane. Of course, the underlying wealth of the complexes and to some extent the possibilities that such obstacle brought to other fields of science and technology are always clear. This article concentrates exclusively on the search for complex solutions to the problem posed. These solutions in the complex plane could have some type of technological application. An important open question which persist: other classes of solutions exist for this problem?

Section 2 includes the first integral complex problem. Section 3 includes the principal result of paper. A family of viscous complex solution was founded that satisfies the first integral complex problem. In section 4, the viability of the new approach is demonstrated by solving two specific examples of complex solutions. Conclusions are drawn in section 5.

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2. Equations

Considering the first integral of the Navier-Stokes equations (Scholle et al. 2011):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{i\rho u^2}{2} + \eta \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} - i \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} &= 0, \\ \Im\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial \bar{z}}\right) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

where u denotes the complex velocity field and $\Phi = \Phi(z, \bar{z})$ the real-valued potential field. The main objective of this paper is to seek solutions for (2.1).

3. Methods: proposition

$F(z)$ is an analytic function and

$$f(z) = \frac{\partial F}{\partial z}, \quad (3.1)$$

Then if we choose Φ so

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} &= -\frac{\rho f(z)}{2R^2(F(z) - z)^2}, \\ R &= \frac{\rho}{2\eta}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

is the typical Reynolds number. Then the complex solution:

$$u = \frac{i}{R(F(z) - z)}, \quad (3.3)$$

is the solution for (2.1).

(a) Demonstration

The proof is directly:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{i\rho}{2} u^2 &= \frac{i\rho}{2} \left(\frac{-1}{R^2(F(z) - z)^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{-i\rho}{2R^2(F(z) - z)^2} \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

also

$$\eta \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \frac{-i\eta}{R^2(F(z) - z)^2} R(F'(z) - 1) \quad (3.5)$$

but

$$\eta R = \frac{\rho}{2}, \quad (3.6)$$

then

$$\eta \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \frac{-i\rho}{2R^2(F(z) - z)^2} (F'(z) - 1) \quad (3.7)$$

Sum (3.7) and (3.4) to is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{i\rho}{2}u^2 + \eta \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} &= \frac{-i\rho}{2R^2(F(z) - z)^2}F'(z) \\ &= \frac{-i\rho f(z)}{2R^2(F(z) - z)^2} \\ &= i \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where the identity is clear. The continuity condition is fulfilled in virtue that the function u is analytic in the points where $F(z)$ is analytic and $F(z) \neq z$.

4. Results: examples of particular solutions

Here we present some particular solutions that satisfy the complex operator. These solutions are represented by elementary functions which makes them interesting. They are valid for the complex plane. It is important to note that there are many solutions to this operator in the complex domain.

(a)

$F(z) \equiv C$ then $f(z) \equiv 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} \equiv 0$ and the dipole solution of (2.1):

$$u = \frac{-i}{Rz} \quad (4.1)$$

For example $\Phi(z) = z\bar{z}$ or $\Phi(z) = z + \bar{z}$.

(b)

$F(z) = z - \frac{1}{\text{senz}}$. Then

$$u = \frac{-i\text{senz}}{R} \quad (4.2)$$

and the potential Φ satisfies:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} &= \frac{-\rho f(z)}{2R^2(F(z) - z)^2} \\ &= \frac{-\rho(1 + \frac{\cos z}{\text{sen}^2 z})}{2R^2(\frac{-1}{\text{senz}})^2} \\ &= \frac{-\rho}{2R^2}(\text{sen}^2 z + \cos z) \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

taking into account the identity $\text{sen}^2 z = \frac{1 - \cos 2z}{2}$ we obtained:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} = \frac{-\rho}{2R^2} \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cos 2z + \cos z \right) \quad (4.4)$$

This last expression allows us to find the second primitive. In effect is:

$$g(z) = \frac{-\rho}{2R^2} \left(\frac{z^2}{4} + \frac{\cos 2z}{8} - \cos z \right) \quad (4.5)$$

then obviously:

$$\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z^2} = \frac{-\rho}{2R^2} \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cos 2z + \cos z \right) \quad (4.6)$$

whereas the identity $g(\bar{z}) = g(z)$ (all coefficients of the Taylor's series of $g(z)$ are reals):

$$\Phi = g(z) + g(\bar{z}) = 2\Re\left(\frac{-\rho}{2R^2}\left(\frac{z^2}{4} + \frac{\cos 2z}{8} - \cos z\right)\right) \quad (4.7)$$

is the potential wanted.

(c)

$F(z) = z^2$. Then

$$u = \frac{i}{Rz(z-1)} \quad (4.8)$$

and by indeterminate coefficients:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} = \frac{\rho}{R^2 z} - \frac{\rho}{R^2(z-1)} + \frac{\rho}{R^2(z-1)^2} \quad (4.9)$$

then the second primitive (already simplified):

$$g(z) = \frac{\rho z}{R^2} \log \frac{z}{z-1} \quad (4.10)$$

With reasonings similar to the previous case we obtain that $\Phi = g(z) + g(\bar{z})$ is a wanted potential and:

$$\Phi = 2\Re\left(\frac{\rho z}{R^2} \log \frac{z}{z-1}\right) \quad (4.11)$$

5. Conclusion

We believe that there is an abundance of solutions, in the complex plane, which conform to the posed problem. Obviously, these solutions are purely mathematical and are not subject to boundary conditions. However, unlike what we know so far, these are viscous solutions, where the Reynolds number is present. Do these solutions have an applied interest? Only the future can answer this question.

Ethics.

Data Accessibility.

Authors' Contributions.

Competing Interests.

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Disclaimer.

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